

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

CEPHALOSPORIN RESISTANT E-COLI CAUSING URINARY TRACT INFECTION

¹Dr. Razia Asif, ²Dr. Ikram din Ujjan, ³Dr. Arshi Naz

¹Department of Pathology & Diagnostic Research Laboratory, Bilawal Medical College Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan, ²Department of Pathology & Diagnostic Research Laboratory, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences Jamshoro, ³National Institute of Blood Disease & Bone Marrow Transplantation Karachi Sindh Pakistan

Article Received: June 2019

Accepted: July 2019

Published: August 2019

Abstract:

Objective: To evaluate the cephalosporin resistant E-coli causing urinary tract infection at Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad / Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan

Patients And Methods: This descriptive case series study was conducted from August 2017 to August 2018 at Department of Microbiology Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences Jamshoro. All the patients with ≥ 01 year of age of either gender presented with fever and chills, headache were recruited and enrolled in the study. All the relevant patients had urine examination, such as urine culture and sensitivity for the presence of urinary tract infection and the pattern of sensitivity and resistance of cephalosporin. The frequency and percentage was calculated for categorical variables and mean $\pm$ SD was calculated for numerical variables. As this was descriptive case series so no statistical test of significance was applied.

Results: During one year study period, total one hundred thirty (130) patients were studied with means age 52.84 ± 8.82 (SD). Of one hundred thirty (130), 57 (43.8%) were males and 73 (56.1%) were females. The sensitivity and resistance for cephalosporin was observed in 30 (23%) and 100 (77%) respectively.

Conclusion: Antimicrobial resistant rates are expanding consistently for cephalosporin expected to apply clinical adequacy in the treatment of UTI because of their far reaching, and mistaken use in our population.

Key Words: Cephalosporin, Antibiotics, UTI

Corresponding author:**Dr. Razia Asif,**

Department of Pathology & Diagnostic Research Laboratory,
Bilawal Medical College Jamshoro Sindh Pakistan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Razia Asif et al., *Cephalosporin Resistant E-Coli Causing Urinary Tract Infection.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[08].

INTRODUCTION:

Urinary tract contamination (UTI) is one of the most widely recognized irresistible ailments observed in the community [1]. Empirical anti-infection regimen is normally connected here and for this, information of the regular uropathogens and their defenselessness to generally utilized anti-infection agents is required [2]. Treatment turns out to be significantly additionally testing within the sight of hazard factors, for example, higher age, co-morbidity, and immunosuppression [3]. Commonly, doctors resort to endorsing expansive range wide spectrum over explicit anti-microbials in the perspective on opposition of the causative living being to the wide spectrum [4]. Poor patient consistence and inadequate course of anti-microbial treatment have brought about the development of protection from a significant number of these wide spectrum agents [5, 6]. Different studies done worldwide have demonstrated changing variety in the etiology of UTIs. There are constrained studies on UTI particularly from Pakistan. Likewise small scale living beings disengaged, present distinctive helplessness pattern to antimicrobial operators, which differ as indicated by where the investigation is performed and furthermore after some time. Henceforth, this survey attempted to decide the cephalosporin resistant e-coli causing urinary tract contamination at tertiary care teaching hospital.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This descriptive case series study was conducted from August 2017 to August 2018 at Department of Microbiology LUMHS Jamshoro. All the participants having age ≥ 1 year either gender complain of pyrexia, headache, and chills were recruited to being explored. All the specific individuals had urine examination, such as urine culture and sensitivity for the presence of urinary tract infection and the pattern of sensitivity and resistance of cephalosporin. The patient already on antibiotics, malignancy and on chemotherapy and the individuals who refused to participate in the study were excluded from the study. The data was saved on proforma and analyzed in SPSS 21 the categorical variables and mean $\pm$ SD were analyzed and computed. Being case series no statistical test of significance was considered to be applied.

RESULTS:

During one year study period, total one hundred thirty (130) patients were studied with mean age (mean $\pm$ SD) as 52.84 ± 8.82 (yrs). The clinical and demographical parameters of study population are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

PARAMETERS	FREQUENCY (n=130)	PERCENTAGE (%)
GENDER		
Male	57	43.8
Female	73	56.1
RESIDENCE		
Urban	45	34.6
Rural	85	65.3
CEPHALOSPORIN		
Sensitive	30	23
Resistant	100	77

DISCUSSION:

Urinary tract contaminations have an across the board circulation worldwide and the significant factor in the improvement of bacterial opposition is the creation of beta-lactamase chemicals by microorganisms [7]. The greater part of the sample acquired from emergency clinic contaminations are impervious to various anti-infection agents. In the present examination almost 77% of clinical secludes were impervious to cephalosporin anti-infection agents with female sexual orientation transcendence (56.1%). The expanding resistant in gram-negative bacilli has caused issues in the exact wide spectrum treatment worldwide. Asia has a long history of express broadened range beta-lactamase (ESBL) delivering microscopic organisms. Likewise it is entrenched that there are numerous distinctions in the pervasiveness and hereditary of ESBLs in medical clinics and particularly in various nations [8]. In a series directed by Mirzaei M, et al [9] and partners the pace of third-age cephalosporin resistant was 56.69% and the most well-known MIC for their group medications. In different series noteworthy contrasts established in the paces of resistant microorganisms than the present study that can be brought about by aimless utilization of ceftriaxone and ceftazidime in our population. For instance, the ceftazidime resistant rate in the series led by Hoban DJ, et al [10] was 14.3% vs 65%, which are altogether different. This worth is for recorded overall disengages. A series was led by Okesola A, et al [11] in Nigeria, the pace of protection from ceftriaxone and ceftazidime has been accounted for, 37.5% and 43.4%, separately. In another survey directed by Tan TY, et al [12] in Singapore, the estimation of ceftriaxone resistant rate that was gotten by disc dispersion technique, expanded to 28%.

CONCLUSION:

Antimicrobial resistant rates are expanding consistently for cephalosporin expected to apply clinical adequacy in the treatment of UTI because of their far reaching, and mistaken use in our population.

REFERENCES:

1. Gupta K, Hooton TM, Stamm WE. Increasing antimicrobial resistance and the management of uncomplicated community-acquired urinary tract infections. *Annals of internal medicine*. 2001 Jul 3;135(1):41-50.
2. Karlowsky JA, Kelly LJ, Thornsberry C, Jones ME, Sahm DF. Trends in antimicrobial resistance among urinary tract infection isolates of *Escherichia coli* from female outpatients in the United States. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*. 2002 Aug 1;46(8):2540-5.
3. Manges AR, Johnson JR, Foxman B, O'Bryan TT, Fullerton KE, Riley LW. Widespread distribution of urinary tract infections caused by a multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* clonal group. *New England journal of medicine*. 2001 Oct 4;345(14):1007-13.
4. Akram M, Shahid M, Khan AU. Etiology and antibiotic resistance patterns of community-acquired urinary tract infections in JNMC Hospital Aligarh, India. *Annals of clinical microbiology and antimicrobials*. 2007 Jan;6(1):4.
5. Foxman B. The epidemiology of urinary tract infection. *Nature Reviews Urology*. 2010 Dec;7(12):653.
6. Hooton TM. Uncomplicated urinary tract infection. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2012 Mar 15;366(11):1028-37.
7. Ronald A. The etiology of urinary tract infection: traditional and emerging pathogens. *The American journal of medicine*. 2002;113(1):14-9.
8. Jahani S, Ghamgosha M, Shakiba A, Hassanpour K, Taheri RA. Assessment of Third Generation Cephalosporin (Ceftazidime and Ceftriaxone) Resistant *Escherichia Coli* Strains Isolated from Zahedan Hospitals by Tracing the TEM Gene. *Journal of Applied Biotechnology Reports*. 2017;4(1):547-52
9. Mirzaee M, Pourmand M, Chitsaz M., Mansouri S, Antibiotic resistance to third generation cephalosporins due to CTX-M-Type extended-spectrum β -lactamases in clinical isolates of *Escherichia coli*. *Iran J Public Health*. 2009;38:10-17.
10. Hoban DJ, Nicolle LE, Hawser S, Bouchillon S, Badal R. Antimicrobial susceptibility of global inpatient urinary tract isolates of *Escherichia coli*: results from the Study for Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance Trends (SMART) program: 2009-2010. *Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2011 Aug;70(4):507-11.
11. Okesola A, Makanjuola O. Resistance to third-generation cephalosporins and other antibiotics by Enterobacteriaceae in Western Nigeria. *Am J Infect Dis*, 2009;5:17-20.
12. Tan TY, Ng LSY, He J, Hsu LY, CTX-M and ampC β -lactamases contributing to increased prevalence of ceftriaxoneresistant *Escherichia coli* in Changi General Hospital, Singapore. *Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2010;66(2):210-3.